

Consent

Welcome!

Thank you for your interest in participating in our survey! This survey is part of a larger research project conducted by faculty at Oberlin College, and funded by the Great Lakes Protection Fund. We are interested in how people think about their water and electricity use, as well as the Oberlin community. This survey will take approximately 10 minutes. To thank you for your time, we will either enter your name in a drawing for a \$50 gift certificate (to be awarded by June 30, 2014) OR you can choose to have \$3 donated to Oberlin Community Services on your behalf.

This survey includes questions about your attitudes water and electricity use, your attitudes about the natural environment, and also about your impression of Oberlin as a community. There are no known risks or benefits involved with the procedures in this study. But if any question makes you uncomfortable, feel free to leave it blank. At the end of the survey, you will be invited to provide contact information to be eligible to participate in a second survey 6 – 12 months from now (at which time you will be eligible for another drawing or donation). You are still eligible for the drawing or donation in this round regardless of whether you choose to be contacted again.

There are no known risks associated with your participation in this research study. The answers and information you provide in this study will remain confidential. Should you participate in the second survey, your data will be matched by using a randomly generated ID number, but your name will never appear in the data set. No one will be able to identify you or your answers. Should the data be published, no individual information will be disclosed. Your participation in this study is completely voluntary. You are free to decline to answer any particular question you do not wish to answer for any reason, and you are free to discontinue participation completely at any point for any reason.

We are happy to provide you a copy of this consent form upon request. If you have any additional questions about the study, please contact Dr. Cindy Frantz, at Cindy.Frantz@oberlin.edu or 440-775-8499. For questions concerning the rights of human subjects, please contact Meredith Raimondo, Chair of the Oberlin Institutional Review Board, at Meredith.Raimondo@oberlin.edu or 440-775-8410.

If you are willing to participate, click below!

- Yes, I am 18 years or older and willing to participate.
- No thanks

Where are you completing this survey?

- Slow Train
- Oberlin Community Services
- Kendal at Oberlin
- Ben Franklin
- OECC
- Oberlin Cable Coop
- Online and not in above locations

Perceptions of others

Rate the degree to which you agree with the following statements:

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Somewhat Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Other people in Oberlin are doing things to make the environment and community in Oberlin better.	<input type="radio"/>					
I think the community and environment in Oberlin will be better in the future.	<input type="radio"/>					
I can do things to make the environment and community in Oberlin better.	<input type="radio"/>					
We can build on Oberlin's past history to improve the community and environment.	<input type="radio"/>					
Oberlin has lots of natural beauty.	<input type="radio"/>					
I know what youth are doing to improve environment and community.	<input type="radio"/>					
I choose to purchase things from local businesses rather than from other sources	<input type="radio"/>					

How much do you think each of the following parts of our community are committed to the environment?

	Not at all committed				Very committed	
	1	2	3	4	5	6
Oberlin businesses	<input type="radio"/>					
Youth	<input type="radio"/>					

	Not at all committed				Very committed	
	1	2	3	4	5	6
Adults	<input type="radio"/>					
The public schools	<input type="radio"/>					
Your friends	<input type="radio"/>					
Your neighbors	<input type="radio"/>					
City workers	<input type="radio"/>					
People working for community organizations	<input type="radio"/>					
Oberlin College	<input type="radio"/>					
The City of Oberlin	<input type="radio"/>					

Sustainability open ended

How often do you spend time thinking about the following?

	Never	Less than	Once a	2-3	Once a	2-3	Daily
		Once a	Month	Times a	Week	Times a	
Oberlin's history	<input type="radio"/>						
Oberlin's youth	<input type="radio"/>						
Oberlin's businesses	<input type="radio"/>						
Oberlin's natural spaces	<input type="radio"/>						
Your neighborhood	<input type="radio"/>						

Organizations

There are many organizations in Oberlin that are working to improve the community. Please rate the following organizations on the 6-point scale according to how familiar you are with the work they are doing.

	Never heard of it				Very familiar	
	1	2	3	4	5	6
Oberlin Community Services	<input type="radio"/>					
POWER (Providing Oberlin With Energy Responsibly)	<input type="radio"/>					
Oberlin Business Partnership	<input type="radio"/>					
Zion CDC (Community Development Corporation)	<input type="radio"/>					
Oberlin Heritage Center	<input type="radio"/>					
The Bridge	<input type="radio"/>					
WAGE (Women Addressing Gender Equality)	<input type="radio"/>					

	Never heard of it				Very familiar	
	1	2	3	4	5	6
CATSS (Community Action to Save Strays)	<input type="radio"/>					

Systems

Everyone has different opinions and experiences. We'd like to know how you see things. For each question below, click on the number that best represents your opinion.

	Not at all				A large amount	
	1	2	3	4	5	6
How much do you think about the water and living things in Plum Creek (the stream in Oberlin)?	<input type="radio"/>					
When you spend money in Oberlin, how much does it affect other people in Oberlin?	<input type="radio"/>					
When other people spend money in Oberlin, how much does it affect you?	<input type="radio"/>					
How much do you feel like you are a valued person in this community?	<input type="radio"/>					
When you are a good citizen, how much does it affect other people?	<input type="radio"/>					
When other people are good citizens, how much does it affect you?	<input type="radio"/>					
When other people take care of nature in Oberlin, how much does it affect you?	<input type="radio"/>					
When you take care of nature in Oberlin, how much does it affect other people?	<input type="radio"/>					
How aware are you about what youth think about environmental issues?	<input type="radio"/>					
How influenced are you by what youth think about environmental issues?	<input type="radio"/>					

Water questions

Everyone has different opinions and experiences. We would like to know how you see things. For each question below, click on the number that best represents your opinion.

	Not at all			A large amount		
	1	2	3	4	5	6
How much do you try to use less water?	<input type="radio"/>					
When you use water, does it affect the environment?	<input type="radio"/>					
Do you think about the amount of water the town of Oberlin uses?	<input type="radio"/>					
Do you think about where the water you use comes from?	<input type="radio"/>					
How much do you try to use less electricity?	<input type="radio"/>					
When you use electricity, does it affect the environment?	<input type="radio"/>					
Do you think about the amount of electricity the town of Oberlin uses?	<input type="radio"/>					
Do you think about where the electricity you use comes from?	<input type="radio"/>					

SignageExposure

Demographics

How often do you normally visit [location]?

- Less than once per month
- Once per month
- 2-3 times per month
- Once per week
- 2-3 times per week
- Daily

What is gender do you identify yourself as?

Male

Female

Other

With what ethnicity do you primarily identify?

- African / African-American
- Asian / Asian-American
- European / European-American ("white")

- Latina/o
- Native American
- Mixed Race
- Other

How long have you lived in Oberlin?

- less than 1 year
- 1-5 years
- 6-10 years
- 10-15 years
- 15-20 years
- more than 20 years
- I do not live in Oberlin

We are interested in knowing the degree to which people living in different parts of the city are represented in this survey. Shown below is a Google map of Oberlin, Ohio. The pin "A" is at the geographic center of town. Please click to indicate on the map below the region in which you live. If you prefer not to indicate approximately where you live or cannot find your location on the map, simply select a location or landmark on the map which indicates a general area or leave this question unanswered.

units

List things that you could do to improve the Oberlin environment and community.

List things that people can do to make Oberlin a more sustainable community.

Would you like us to donate \$3 to Oberlin Community Services on your behalf or have your name entered into a raffle for a \$50 gift certificate to downtown Oberlin businesses?

- Donation to Oberlin Community Services
- Raffle entry

What is your email address?

What is your name?

As part of this study we are trying to measure how views towards environment and community change over time in Oberlin. Would you be willing to participate in follow-up surveys? Signing up does not obligate you to participate. Your information will not be shared with any other groups or used for any other purpose. If you are willing to participate in future surveys please click the box below.

- Yes, I am willing to be contacted in the future for additional studies
- No, I would prefer to be left off of the list of potential participants